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Corporate Culture Strategy in Human Resource Management Practice: Indonesia Perspective

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Abstract: This study examines the corporate culture strategically introduced by human resource managers to discuss cultural differences between parent companies, subsidiaries, and individuals. Semi-structured interview with 8 human resource managers (HR) in Indonesia. The company's strategic culture includes the level of standardization of human resources, industrial relations, and geographical differences. To implement corporate culture strategies in human resource practices, managers promote stronger partnerships with subsidiaries, standardize human resource management practices, focus on changes in labor legislation, educational and cultural development, leadership development and cultural awareness.

Keywords: Strategies, Corporate Culture, Human Resources Practices

1. INTRODUCTION

The acquisition decision aims to achieve product synergy. The success of the acquisition is related to the corporate culture. Schein (2010, 7) has defined that culture is “an abstraction, but the power emerging from culture in social and organizational situations is very strong.” Hofstede (2010) describes four cultural manifestations, namely: symbols; hero; ritual; and values. The success of acquisitions in cultural contexts has three cultural categories, namely; corporate culture (Schein, 2010), corporate sub-culture (Hofstede, 2010) and individual culture (Erez and Gati, 2014). It explains that the corporate culture embraces the values, beliefs, attitudes, and norms of the company plays. That is an important role in conducting best human resource management (HR) practices.

In the realm of corporate culture, the company is still conducting trials to implement human resource management policies and practices while respecting the customs and traditions of its subsidiaries (Chen and Eldridge, 2010). Furthermore, human resource managers must understand labor regulations at both the regional and national levels (O'Sullivan, 2010; Posthuma *et al.*, 2006). Managers working in subsidiaries

(corporate subcultures) will have difficulty adjusting (Robbins and Judge, 2013). On the other hand, HR managers look for corporate culture strategies that make their organizations successful. Implement a strategic corporate culture in the parent company to ensure that the organization embodies the values, goals and objectives supported by human resources policies, procedures and practices (Brewster and Suutari, 2005, Labeledz and Lee, 2011).

In the realm of corporate subculture, a lack of general knowledge of intercultural business ethics has been seriously weakened corporate subcultures (Shapiro *et al.*, 2008). Corporate subcultures strategies related to issues of trade union negotiations in subsidiaries (Millar and Choi, 2008). While, the domain of individual culture, there are many issues related to managers and employees of subsidiaries. In such cases, a major source of the failure is often a lack of cultural understanding of a subsidiary, as Selmer (2006) pointed out the geographical differences, although there might miscommunication between subsidiary and parent employees. Individual cultural strategy disseminates vision and mission of the parent company to foster a unified mindset of diversity among employees through human resource competencies development and business-related competencies beyond the geographic boundaries (Levy *et al.*, 2007).

In the parent structure, HR managers need to align HR policies and procedures with business objectives. The strategies implemented are knowledge of the limitations in standardization of HR policies and procedures across subsidiaries (Bjorkman and Budhwar, 2007; Dalton and Druker, 2012). Although there are several policies that can apply to all subsidiaries, it is difficult to execute corporate culture strategies in the parent structure of companies with subcultures of subsidiaries, due to local uniqueness (Levy *et al.*, 2007).

The main focus of this research is corporate culture strategy in the practice of Human Resource Management (HRM), with sub-focus on internalization of corporate culture, HRM practice standardization, labor negotiations, and geographical differences. The purpose of this research is to understand corporate culture strategy in practice of HRM in overcoming business competition. Our research contributes to HRM practices development by integrating the corporate culture into the parent structure, subsidiaries and culture of individual employees to meet business challenges. For the purposes of this study, we constructed semi-structured interview questionnaires, by interviewing 8 HR managers from various industries. The corporate culture strategy in the HRM literature and organizational behavior focuses on the company's values, goals, and objectives in the face of business competition, a key task of HR managers in implementing the best HRM practices for the company's sustainability.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Corporate Culture

Institutional theory suggests that an organization adapts as a result of local uniqueness to improve the survival of the company (Jackson and Deeg, 2008; Pajunen, 2008). When the researchers used the Hofstede cultural dimension in studying the behavior of individual managers, it was found that individuals as group members had characteristics that were different from the average group in general (Berry *et al.*, 2010). Thus, HR managers need creative in achieving business goals through HR policies and practices while respecting local customs and traditions.

The corporate culture strategy of the parent company is the management of diversity, especially regarding the expectations of people in the workplace. Different individuals within the same organizational unit do not always respond the same HRM practices in the company. Diverse cultures lead to communication and conflict difficulties (Dalton and Druker, 2012; Das, 2010). Different communication styles between managers in the parent company and employees in subsidiaries a source of conflict in the workplace (Forstenlechner, 2010). According to Schein (2010), communication conflicts exacerbated by the context of people interacting. For example, Individual characteristics derived from a subsidiary culture with explicit and logical communication styles (communication style of North Sumatra). Conversely, people who come from the culture of parents tend to communicate with non-verbal style (communication style of Java). Therefore, managers of parent companies must have the knowledge, skills and ability to control communication in the workplace to improve work productivity.

The subcultural strategy of the branch office consists of effective promotion of virtual teams. New information and communications technologies make it possible to coordinate meetings and knowledge sharing between regions (Kapoor, 2011). Although often regarded as a more effective way of communicating, the use of virtual teams is hampered by cultural differences (Graf *et al.*, 2010). For example, the lack of physical contact may affect confidence (Elron and Viga-Gadot, 2006). In another study, Dekker *et al.* (2008) focuses on virtual teams that use Hofstede's cultural dimensions and find that team members' perceptions vary from culture to culture.

The structure of individual employees such as appropriate selection of managers, personnel considerations, intercultural training and development, attractive salary levels, performance appraisals and management, productive employment relationships, talent management and effective repatriation (Hofstede, 2010; Schein, 2010, Shapiro *et al.*, 2008). It is also recognized that the family members accompanying a branch manager are part of the professional success of the manager (Littrell *et al.*, 2006). Therefore, HR managers need to focus on the welfare of managers to maximize the success of branch operations. Indeed, many studies have shown that programs that use cultural theories (such as integrating knowledge about different cultures, educational cultures and cultural sensitivities) tend to better prepare managers for activities in the affiliate field.

2.2. The Role of Human Resource Management

The role of human resources as a strategic business partner is well known (Labeledz and Lee, 2011, Pritchard, 2010). In this partnership, HR provides important and important services to organizations in various forms, such as: B. Development of skills, skills and competencies, leadership development, change management and knowledge management (Burbach and Royle, 2010 Hertog *et al.*, 2010). The role of human resources becomes important to ensure that any personal policies and practices contribute to corporate value (Boohene and Asuinura, 2011). Therefore, human resource development is fundamental as part of the business matrix and the strategic role of the human resources department can be assessed and human resources can utilize feedback to improve the overall business. To play the role of strategic business partners, HR managers must understand the role of mutual support of subsidiary activities (such as finance, marketing and operations).

Connecting with strategic business partners involves the human resource skills associated with the company. Human resources must understand business issues and contribute to management change through proactive participation (Hertog *et al.*, 2010; Levy *et al.*, 2007). An example is excellent customer recognition

performance through talent management in the affiliate field through collaboration with parent marketing departments (Hughes and Rog, 2008). It is said, HR knows the business well to serve customers. The human resources skills associated with the company have been developed through professional development practices such as job redesign, work enrichment and work rotation (Wood and Wall, 2007). With the growth of the company, the development of the conscious cultural skills for individual managers is critical to the success of the organization (Graf and Mertesacker, 2009). Therefore, there is a personal need that has expertise and business experience.

Another important role of HR managers is to harmonize the policies and procedures of the parent and subsidiary human resources. Given that environmental, sociocultural, and regulatory differences can affect HR policies and procedures standardization. Therefore, HR managers flexible in implementing HR policies and procedures with colleagues in subsidiaries (Almond, 2011; Björkman and Lervik, 2007; Pudelko, 2006). Pudelko and Harzing (2008) provide several examples that illustrate human resources in its branches. For example, instead of implementing a time-dependent payment system, as in Japan, Canon introduced performance-oriented strategies in the United States. Kopp (2006) found that Japanese organizations tend to use practices that involve acting ethnocentric organizations in America and Europe. Therefore, the corporate culture strategy in the form of best human resource management practices, which has produced conflicting results in providing a competitive advantage.

3. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

As discussed above, the conceptual framework of this research is the corporate culture strategy in the practice of HR, with sub-focus on the internalization of corporate culture, HR practice standardization, labor negotiations, and geographical differences. The purpose of this research is to understand corporate culture strategy in practice of HR in overcoming business competition. Our research can contribute to HR practices development by integrating the corporate culture into the parent structure, subsidiaries and individual culture of employees in responding to business challenges. The results of Ngo and Loi (2008) suggest that employee behavior and HR practices flexibility have strong links with cultural adaptation.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1. Sampling Design

The authors interviewed 8 senior HR managers in various industries in Indonesia. Table 1 summarizes the participants' background. Participants are selected by author's personal contact. Two conditions of eligibility are the responsibility of national human resources. Three quarters of participants from Jakarta. The manager works in various industries, including manufacturing, banking, financing, information technology, healthcare, food products, mining and pharmaceuticals. Permission for interview recordings for transcription purposes is given before beginning the interview.

4.2. Research Procedure

Interviews conducted using interviewer criteria recommended by Denzin and Lincoln (2005). These criteria include the knowledge of the theme and arrangement in interview to facilitate the interview process and make sure the question is clear, taking into account the ethics of the interview (such as solving the first

Table 1
Participant Background Summary

<i>Participant</i>	<i>Industry</i>	<i>City</i>	
		<i>Parent company</i>	<i>Subsidiaries</i>
JWE	Manufacture	South Sulawesi	Jakarta
AST	Pharmacy	Jakarta	East Nusa Tenggara
BGH	Health	Jakarta	West Papua
TDF	Banking	Jakarta	South Borneo
JKM	Information Technology	Jakarta	North Maluku
SWD	Food product	Surabaya	Jakarta
HSL	Mining	West Sumatra	Borneo
TTJ	Financing	Jakarta	North Borneo

question before moving on to the next question and listening intently), being open which is important interviewed.

On average, the interviews seized 45 minutes and the interview schedule emailed to participants a week before the interview schedule, then participants have time to think about Pseudoni's questions for the individuals and organizations used in this study for the purposes of secrecy. Interviews consist of 6 open-ended questions. Questions relevant to this paper include national business strategies after the national financial crisis, the strategic implications faced by the HR division and the negotiation strategies employed. Interview structures used in semi-open structured format, to enable unexpected and emerging themes. This method also allows follow-up and inquiry questions by clarifying key issues and allows participants to freely express their grievances. This research is a qualitative study with open interviews, then find a new conceptualization of human resource management practices (Welch et al., 2008).

5. DATA ANALYSIS

Each interview is transcribed with words and analyzed with Nvivo software (version 8), which is often used to organize and analyze unstructured qualitative data. Bazeley and Jackson (2013) note that Nvivo can provide more stiffness and traceability than manual encoding and is useful for identifying emerging categories and topics. Given the usefulness of Nvivo in thematic analysis (Bazeley and Jackson, 2013), this strategy has been used to find words, phrases and phrases that form a common theme in all 8 cases. This leads to a series of early codes (Miles et al., 2014) with two main categories, strategies and corporate culture. This technique uses free encoding that reduces distortion compared to single coding use (Miles et al., 2014), continuous discussion between code and three iterations, interrelated relationships identified and divided into two main components (ie strategy and corporate culture).

6. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

6.1. Conclusion

The findings in this study help HRD practitioners to understand how employees see diversity ranging from education, religion, ethnicity, to economics. It provides insights into the effects of individual, employment

and organizational factors that related to corporate culture strategies. Other than that, dynamic business environment, this research adds knowledge of HR practitioners and managers to assist employees in the process of aligning corporate culture, corporate subcultures, and individual cultures on performance and career. We further conclude that individuals and organizations should take into account conformity between the individual context, and the environment in the company's acquisition decisions. Therefore, management must assess various issues; standardization of HR policies and procedures; negotiation with unions in subsidiaries; and resolve communication conflicts due to geographical differences.

Therefore, academia and professionals must apply the corporate culture, subcultures and individual cultural categories to gain a deeper understanding of job rotation, job decline and job transformation issues. Although the existing literature addresses the problems found in this study, current research shows the role of human resource managers in implementing corporate culture in all the underlying business areas. Therefore, there are implications for HR managers in terms of prioritizing problems. Recent research conducted by 8 human resource managers from various sectors in Indonesia have examined how managers from other countries apply the same or different corporate culture strategies, since many contemporary cultural studies have found a mix of transnational convergence and divergence.

6.2. Discussion

In the parent and subsidiary structures, the main strategy for managers balanced between standardization of the parent and subsidiary. Some companies have sought to adopt policies and practices (standards) in the affiliate field. If the policies and practices of the organization are well served, there are strong reasons to defend them. However, managers recognize that standardizing human resource policies and practices due to socio-cultural, political and political constraints of parent companies is impractical to allow affiliates to serve their stakeholders through subcultures (local culture). Some have suggested that organizations are interested in HR best practices and the following two comments reflect this challenge in the Corporate Culture category:

"It's already a balance between the parent management coordination and implementation in the subsidiary, and you see the parent company that does not do it well" (Interview JWE, 21/7/15).

"It is important to ensure that our subsidiaries understand the national interest as a whole, that is one of the biggest challenges in our organization" (Interview AST, 26/10/15).

The second strategy for the corporate culture category, the human resource manager interviewed, refers to the employment relationship. Because different regions have different employment laws, a manager states that this is an important task for human resources "to continue to follow different labor laws in different regions". The role of trade unions and their influence structures in other sectors can also impact trade union negotiations. Therefore, while organizational policies are similar, policy implementation is different. Complete standardization and human resource policies are impossible, and the following two quotes capture the difficulty of achieving universal coherence in negotiations with trade unions:

"Labor negotiations are a bit challenging. The union environment in subsidiaries is different from the parent company" (interview BGH, 18/9/15).

TDF: "The ability to get some professional people from to some difficult terrain. Some have no competence as managers" (TDF interview, 2/8/15).

Third strategy, the managers of the parent company must deal with different geographical areas. Consultation with decision makers representing challenges due to geographical differences. Consequently, there are consequences of productivity. Although technology has enabled people to connect virtually, there is still a reliance on managers who are willing to make their personal communication outside of business hours. Therefore, people who are part of a virtual team or have national responsibility must remain flexible. An example of many managers managing the geographic differences described by two managers:

“This requires a little more detail as a manager to coordinate certain people in the affiliate field, but technology must have the resources to do so” (interview JKM, 21/8/15).

SWD: “The challenges of work encountered are geographic barriers”, “North-Sulawesi is the most generous to work and willing to meetings at 9 pm, 10 pm or 11 pm” (SWD interview, 15/9/15).

The company’s subcultural strategy, dealing with sub-culture differences with corporate culture. Difficulties in handling different cultures by managers with the following quote:

“It is very difficult for them to adapt to the culture” (HSL Interview, 7/9/15).

“Day-to-day challenges of cultural work adjustment include individual integration of different cultures” (Interview of TTD, 20/8/15).

Given that employees are in a subsidiary, this challenge a daily challenge. The most visible cultural difference is the style of work. However, whether this task execution can provide services to customers or other employees, an understanding of the cultural nuances in subsidiaries will enable the subsidiaries successful.

Although there is an understanding of the strategies used by parents, the latest literature has two flaws. On the one hand, most studies consider questions in the individual structure of employees (Burbach and Royle, 2010). Second, most studies assume that the organization has the time and budget to develop a global payback program (Edwards & Rees, 2011, Littrell et al., 2006). Therefore, this study examines the strategy of the parent company, subsidiaries and employees of corporate culture strategy, taking into account the reality of the organization within a certain period of time and specific budget constraints. Rather than identifying corporate strategies and cultures, this study seeks to understand the practice of human resources at the national level and how they apply the strategy.

In the main structure, three strategic issues have been identified. Strategic policies and practices in several HR locations. First, even though managers recognize that standardization is impossible for everyone, given the social, cultural, educational, religious, ethnic and economic differences, there is a desire to harmonize policies and practices between parents and subsidiaries. Strategic alignment of human resources through the establishment of partnerships with subsidiaries. In-depth consultation is needed to test for coherence in the harmonization of policies and practices. Another approach to achieve better targeting is the rotation of managers and managers selected by affiliates. They can develop a comprehensive mindset through learning and workplace development. By finding different situations, these leaders are better able to recognize and understand what works in different places and do not work. Given the policies and practices of human resources within the organization, these results are in accordance with institutional theory (Sub and Kleiner, 2008).

Second, it refers to negotiations at work in its branches. Given different laws and work practices in each region, some human resource policies and practices need to be temporarily and others may need to be

negotiated. The proposed consultation process for strategic management should also include discussion of employers 'and workers' reports. Networks and girls should improve communication and knowledge sharing. It is important for HR managers and other managers to know the labor relations and labor laws.

Third, it is important to overcome geographical differences. Sometimes parents and branches need to coordinate closely to ensure timely completion of the project and with a willingness to sacrifice personal time for business meetings, both day and night. At the same time, it is important for managers to understand that people from different cultures have little difference in attitudes toward time differences between Jakarta and Papua. In this study, the adoption of flexible time attitude as positive. Therefore, managers must balance the need to complete their projects.

In the category of corporate subculture, the distinction between cultures is a separate strategy: some parents are responsible for rotational changes because of the inability to adapt cultures. Cultural differences can manifest as differences in work style and communication. Cultural differences can also affect leadership styles, individual responsibility and teamwork. While these results are not new, these challenges are still faced by many modern global managers, including HR managers. Ignoring this difference can lead to conflict between employees. Human resources help provide the necessary cultural education. If special training is required (eg language training), with external training, if internal training is not supported.

Leadership development is another area that must be taken seriously by human resources. A common reason why managers turn to parent companies is their inability to adapt. Although the emphasis on leadership and development training in colleges and universities (Roehling et al., 2005), normative institutional processes (or similarities arising from professional and professional roles) are not clear in this study and may require more time to relieve, careful selection and use before the use of culturally-rooted activities is still required before the work is completed. A realistic preview of the work during the training and development phase is also needed so that potential leaders and their families can prepare for various situations, such as overtime in the workplace. Whenever possible, short-term tasks have been used to give managers a sense of their lifestyle. People who show talent, above all openness and adaptability, work within the context of the subculture selected for further development before being changed.

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